

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of D(—) Ribose by Chloramine-T

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The kinetics of the oxidation of D(—) ribose by chloramine-T has been investigated in high alkaline media. The reaction shows a brief induction period after which first order dependence in both chloramine-T and D(—) ribose is followed. The order in [OH⁻] ion is observed as fractional being 1.35 under the experimental conditions. The activation parameters viz. energy of activation and entropy of activation have been computed as 26.0 k cal mole⁻¹ and +22.2 e.u. respectively. A mechanism involving a termolecular rate controlling step among hypochlorite ion, hydroxide ion and anion derived from β-anomer of D(—) ribose explains the experimental results very well.

OXIDATION of some reducing sugars has been studied by several workers¹⁻⁴. Ingles and Israel⁵ studied the kinetics of oxidation of several aldoses by iodine in alkaline media and supposed undissociated hypoiodous acid as the main oxidising agent. The oxidation of anomericly equilibrated glucose⁶ by chlorine was studied in buffered acid solutions at 35.7°C. The kinetic results of the reaction showed a first order dependence in both the oxidant and glucose concentrations. Capon⁷ in an excellent review on carbohydrate mechanisms has discussed the mechanism of oxidation of aldoses by bromine. The studies on the kinetics of the oxidation of some reducing sugars by several oxidants⁸⁻⁹ have also been made.

In the present communication, the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of D(—) ribose by chloramine-T in alkaline media has been investigated.

Experimental

Aqueous solution of D(—) ribose (B.D.H., B.C.) was always freshly prepared. Stock solutions of chloramine-T, osmium (VIII) and sodium hydroxide were prepared as mentioned earlier¹⁰. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade. Doubly distilled water was always employed for preparation and dilution of the solutions. The reactions were

carried out in Jena glass reaction bottles blackened from outside.

The kinetics were followed by estimating the aliquot portions of the reaction mixture for chloramine-T iodometrically¹¹ using starch as an indicator. The alkali-ribose mixture was allowed to equilibrate for exactly 45 minutes after which chloramine-T was added to start the reaction.

Stoichiometry

Reaction mixtures containing excess of chloramine-T over ribose were allowed to equilibrate at 45° in sodium hydroxide solution of suitable concentration. The results showed that one mole of chloramine-T oxidised one mole of sugar to the aldonic acid and thus the stoichiometric equation may be represented as :

Results

It is observed that the oxidation of D(—) ribose by chloramine-T shows a marked induction period. The influence of the change in equilibrating time of the mixture of ribose-alkali on the induction period

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was studied. The results show that the induction period diminishes as the equilibrating time is increased and after 45 minutes of the equilibrating time, it almost disappears (Fig. 1). After this period a first order dependence in chloramine-T is followed.

Fig. 1. First order plots at 32.5°. [D(—) Ribose]= 2.0×10^{-2} M, [Chloramine-T]= 2.0×10^{-3} M, [NaOH]=0.05 M and equilibrating time=0, 15, 30 and 45 minutes for A, B, C and D respectively.

The kinetics of the oxidation of ribose by chloramine-T was investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants (Table 1). The results show a first order dependence in chloramine-T. Pseudo first order rate constants (k_1) in chloramine-T, calculated from the slope of the linear log-time plots, increase linearly with the increase of ribose concentration. The second order rate constants, $k_2 = k_1/[\text{ribose}]$ were calculated and the average value was obtained as $10.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for the oxidation of ribose. The slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [D(-)]$

TABLE 1 [NaOH]=0.05M, EQUILIBRATING TIME=45 MINUTES AND TEMP. 32.5°

$10^2[\text{Chloramine-T}]$ M	$10^2[\text{Ribose}]$ M	$k_1 \times 10^5$ sec^{-1}	$k_2 \times 10^3$ $\text{l mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$
2.0	2.0	21.1	10.6
2.4	2.0	20.9	10.5
2.8	2.0	19.9	10.0
3.2	2.0	19.0	9.50
2.0	1.0	10.8	10.8
2.0	1.3	12.8	9.85
2.0	1.6	17.3	10.7
2.0	2.5	23.6	9.44
2.0	3.0	29.9	9.97

ribose] (Fig. 2) was found to be unity which establishes a first order dependence in ribose concentration.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [D(-) \text{ Ribose}]$, conditions same as in Table 1 at [Chloramine-T]= 2.0×10^{-3} M.

Hydroxide ion dependence : The kinetic studies were made at several initial concentrations of alkali at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1$). It was observed that the rate of oxidation of ribose is highly susceptible to a change in OH^- ion concentration. It was found that the order in $[\text{OH}^-]$, calculated from the slope of the plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{OH}^-]$, is 1.35 (Fig. 3) for this reaction.

Fig. 3. Plot of $\log k_1$ vs $\log [\text{OH}^-]$ at [D(—) ribose]= 2.0×10^{-2} M, [Chloramine-T]= 2.0×10^{-3} M, equilibrating time=45 min, $\mu=0.1$ and temp. 32.5°.

Effect of neutral salts : The effect of neutral salts viz. NaClO_4 and KCl , was investigated (Table 2). The results show that this reaction exhibits a positive salt effect.

TABLE 2 [CHLORAMINE-T]= 2×10^{-3} M, [RIBOSE]= 2.0×10^{-2} M, [NaOH]=0.05M, equilibrating time=45 minutes, and temp. = 32.5°

μ	$k_1 \times 10^5 \text{ sec}^{-1}$	
	KCl	NaClO ₄
0.05	24.2	26.1
0.10	31.2	27.3
0.20	39.5	34.5
0.40	48.2	41.8

Dielectric constant effect : A negligible effect of dielectric constant of the media on the reaction rate was observed. Unlike the oxidation of some aliphatic ketones¹⁰ and α -hydroxy acids¹², osmium (VIII) ions were found to be inactive as a catalyst on the rate of the oxidation of ribose by chloramine-T.

Temperature dependence : The effect of temperature on the rate constants was quite marked. The values of the various activation parameters viz. energy of activation, frequency factor and entropy of activation obtained as 26.0 k. cal mole⁻¹, $6.4 \times 10^{17} \text{ l mole}^{-1} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and +22.2 e.u. respectively, were calculated from the Arrhenius plot at five different temperatures ($32.5^\circ - 42.5^\circ$).

Discussion

It is well known that aldoses in alkaline solutions exist as anions derived from β -anomers^{13,14}. Thus the following steps are involved :

The anomerisation step (2a) is a slow process and therefore, restricts the formation of aldose anion step (2b). The anion of aldose is supposed to be the more reacting species.

In alkaline solutions¹⁵, chloramine-T (CAT) hydrolyses as :

where CAT' and TSA represent for *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and *p*-toluene sulphonamide respectively.

It is seen from equation (3a) and (3b) that any one of the hydrolysis products of chloramine-T viz. chloramine-T, itself, *p*-toluenesulphochloramide and hypochlorite ion (ClO⁻) may be involved as the main oxidising species. It has been proposed earlier¹⁶ that CAT' would be involved as the reacting species for acid catalysed reactions only. Further, a positive salt effect clearly points out to the fact that ClO⁻ ion would occur in the slowest and rate controlling step.

Thus, the first order dependence of the reaction rate in each chloramine-T and aldose and the fractional order (1.35) dependence in hydroxide ion leads to the contention that the rate determining step involves the anion of aldose, hypochlorite ion and hydroxide ion. As the C-H bond C(I) is usually ruptured during the formation of the open chain aldonic acid anion, the following steps are involved :

The mechanism of the oxidation of D(-) ribose(S) by chloramine-T in alkaline media may, therefore, be summarised as follows :

In the above scheme step (2) is also slow but not as slow as the rate determining step (4). On adding aldose to the alkali solution, the concentration of aldose anion (S⁻) increases with time. After some time when S⁻ becomes sufficiently high, the consumption of S⁻ in step (4) becomes regular and steady state is achieved. The steady-state in oxidation of aldoses is thus, not achieved instantaneously as has also been observed in the first order plots (Fig. 1) where there are induction period effects. As the alkali-aldose mixture has been equilibrated for 45 minutes for this investigation, the induction period has completely vanished. It has also been experimentally observed that the induction period minimises on increasing the temperature of the reaction mixture.

Applying steady-state conditions to (S⁻) the rate of disappearance of ClO⁻ is given as

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[ClO^-] = \frac{k_3 k_5 [S] [ClO^-] [OH^-]^2}{k_{-3} [H_2O] + k_5 [ClO^-] [OH^-]} \quad (5)$$

In high alkaline solution ClO⁻ may be taken as CAT and thus equation (5) becomes

$$-\frac{d}{dt}[CAT] = \frac{k_3 k_5 [S] [CAT] [OH^-]^2}{k_{-3} [H_2O] + k_5 [CAT] [OH^-]} \quad (6)$$

The derived rate law equation (6) predicts first order dependence in both chloramine-T and aldose and a fractional order in hydroxide ion concentration. At very low concentration of alkali when $k_{-3} [H_2O] \gg k_5 [CAT] [OH^-]$, the order in OH⁻ would be

2 and at very high alkali concentration when $k_{-3} [H_2O] \ll k_5 [CAT] [OH^-]$, the dependence of the reaction rate on alkali would be unity. However, at a reasonable concentration of alkali, both the conditions are not achieved and thus the reaction shows a fractional order dependence in [OH⁻] being 1.35. Further, from equation (6), the rate constant should decrease with increase in chloramine-T concentration which has also been observed experimentally (Table 1).

The positive salt effect also confirms the rate controlling step (4). Since the rate determining step involves three similarly charged ions, a high energy of activation value is expected and this is in agreement with the high experimental observed value viz. 26 kcal mole⁻¹ for the oxidation of ribose by chloramine-T.

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